

Exploring the Shift in Broadcast Media Influence on Voters

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Abstract

Situated within the theoretical framework of uses and gratifications, the study examined the transition of media influence from the predominant conventional media platforms, particularly, television as one of the viable information sources for voters, to digital platforms. The study solely relied on secondary data through the review of relevant literature to examine the factors(s) which account for the shift of media influence and to understand the challenges facing the shift in media influence on voters, from television to digital media. The study revealed that accessibility, network effect and the interactivity nature of digital media, which empower every user to contribute to political discourse, are the reasons for the swing. However, the possibility of digital media to promote information disorder such as fake news, deep fake, misinformation and disinformation are among the trials of the transition. This is because digital media platforms lack the regimented chains of gatekeepers that fortify conventional media against avoidable infractions and the incidences of fake news. The researchers concluded that the shift in the source of media influence on voters is real. It recommended media literacy skills and new legal framework as part of the measures to address all forms of misapplication of digital media platforms for political gains.

Keywords: Television, Media Influence, Digital Media, Voters, Election

Introduction

The mass media are channels of mass communication that fused the world into single entity (Paul & Rai, 2021). They are basically classified into two broad categories of print and electronic media. Rabi (n.d.) is of the view that though people could extract information from any other medium, but print family of media particularly, newspaper is the most authoritative medium of mass communication, given its editorial quality. But Ibbi & Furomfate (2021) observe that the electronic media which encompasses radio, TV and film, regarded as either auditory or audio-visual mediums play equally remarkable role in every society.

According to Ibbi & Furomfate (2021), against the backdrop of their penetrative and persuasive nature, these genres of mass communication hold relative potential of influence on audience and they are considered as powerful. Seibure & Javombo (2018) reason very strongly that the role of the media in every given society is to educate, inform and enlighten. Expectedly, where these roles are upheld and efficiently carried out, elections are likely to be free and fair. Underscoring the enormous values media brought